

Enhancing Safety Climate through Occupational Safety and Health Training in the Healthcare Setting: The mediating Role of Safety Communication

Subash Ghimire¹, Anjay Kumar Mishra², Amiya Bhaumik³

¹Research Scholar, Lincoln University College, Petaling Jaya, Malaysia

²Dean, Faculty of Management, Madesh University, Professor, Birgunj, Nepal

³Dean, Faculty of Business, Lincoln University College, Petaling Jaya, Malaysia

*Corresponding author email ID: subashghimire85@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) training on the safety climate within healthcare settings, emphasizing the mediating role of OSH communication. Healthcare workers are exposed to numerous occupational risks, making effective OSH strategies crucial for fostering a positive safety culture. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 250 healthcare professionals—including doctors, nurses, and technical staff—via a structured questionnaire assessing perceptions of OSH training, OSH communication, and safety climate. The relationships among these variables were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) and SPSS software to conduct impact, correlation, and mediation analyses.

Findings indicate that OSH training has a significant direct positive effect on both OSH communication ($\beta = 0.54$) and safety climate ($\beta = 0.52$). Additionally, OSH communication positively influences safety climate ($\beta = 0.25$). Mediation analysis reveals that OSH communication partially mediates the relationship between OSH training and safety climate, suggesting that the effectiveness of training is enhanced when accompanied by clear, consistent communication regarding safety issues within the organizational context.

These results underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive OSH training programs with strategic communication initiatives to cultivate a favorable safety climate in healthcare environments. The dual influence of training and communication offers practical implications for hospital administrators aiming to improve safety culture and reduce occupational hazards. By prioritizing both components, healthcare institutions can strengthen their capacity to protect workers and enhance overall organizational safety performance.

Keywords: healthcare setting, mediation analysis, occupational safety and health, safety climate, structural equation modeling (SEM)